

Load frequency control for multi-area power system with two-source using sliding mode control

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ABSTRACT

A consistent electrical supply relies on the stability of power systems. In changing load conditions, control methods like load frequency control (LFC) are essential for safeguarding its stability. Conventional methods of LFC frequently encounter uncertainties in the system, external disruptions, and nonlinearities. This article introduces a more sophisticated method for managing load frequency and improving LFC in power systems through the utilization of sliding mode control (SMC). SMC provides strong stability and resilience against nonlinearities and disturbances, making it a promising method to overcome the drawbacks of traditional control techniques. We offer an in-depth examination of the second-order-integral SMC (SOISMC) method specifically designed for LFC, covering the creation and execution of the control algorithm. The method being suggested utilizes a sliding/gliding surface to maintain the system trajectories as continuous on the surface even with changes in parameters and external disturbances. Simulation results show big enhancements in frequency stability and system performance when compared to conventional proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers. The article also features a comparison between SOISMC and other contemporary control methods, emphasizing its strength in terms of resilience and flexibility.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the growing process of industrialization and modernization, the demand for electrical energy is constantly increasing. This poses challenges to maintaining stable frequencies in multi-source, multi-area power interconnected systems (MSMAIPS) with frequent generation and load variations fluctuations. Frequency instability can affect the power system's (PS) operation and reliability. Large frequency deviations can affect the lifespan of equipment, causing system imbalance or overloading the transmission line, affecting the protection ability of the system, and eventually leading to damage to electrical equipment. To solve these load frequency control problems (LFCP), load frequency control (LFC) has been applied.

Various approaches of classical proportional (P), proportional-integral (PI), and proportional-integral-derivative (PID) have been made throughout recent years. A Laurent series-based PID controller controls single and multi-area PS in [1]. A fuzzy PI/PID controller is used with integration of differential evolution and pattern search for optimized gains in [2]. A second-order neural network is also employed to tackle

LFCP in multi-microgrid PS [3]. Cascaded controllers such as fractional-order-PI and fractional-order-PD are proposed to control a hydro-thermal PS in [4]. A PID controller is compared by using an adaptive fuzzy logic controller with H_∞ criterion in [5]. These approaches improve the reactivity and optimize the controllers in order to reduce and converge the area control error with frequency deviation to zero as fast as possible.

The model predictive control (MPC) approach is also widely used for LFCP. An MPC controls MS-MAIPS with consideration of generate rate constraints (GRC) in [6]. Another approach uses disturbance rejection for MSMAIPS in [7]. Furthermore, in [8], an MPC is also used for PS with renewable energy - wind energy. By advancing MPC, adaptive MPC with Kalman filter is used for high-penetration renewable energy microgrids in [9]. An LMI-delay margin estimation-based controller for PS with communication delay is presented in [10]. An event-triggered-based controller is used for PS with time delay in [11]. These researches provide deep understanding of various control methods on many PS scenarios.

The sliding mode control (SMC) approach greatly increases the robustness of control in LFCP. Therefore, in recent years, SMC has been used in various research on LFCP. Many applications of SMC are introduced in [12]. The chattering problem of SMC is rejected due to the successful implementation of second-order SMC in [13]. A second-order SMC with the extended observer is used for robust LFC in [14]. Furthermore, third-order SMC with state observer is developed in [15]. SMC is also used for PS with the cooperation of wind power and time-delay consideration in [16]. Research in [17] does the same thing but tops it off with droop and pitch angle control then proceeds to test it using the IEEE 39 bus system. Another second-order SMC with adaptive behavior and communication-delay PS is investigated in [18]. Battery energy storage system (BESS) is also used with SMC in [19]. Classical SMC is further optimized by smart algorithms such as grey wolf optimization (GWO) and particle swarm optimization (PSO) in [20]. Adaptive high-order SMC is also applied in [21]. Linear matrix inequality (LMI) approach for the dynamic integral SMC with consideration of time delay is researched in [22]. Backstepping-based SMC is proposed in [23] and compared with other advanced SMCs. Electrical vehicle aggregators are considered for LFCP in [24] and modified PSO-based Integral SMC is used. A H_∞ state feedback for SMC with delayed communication is developed in [25]. These SMC controllers deal with many types of LFC problems and the SMC controller problem itself, promoting high stability of the PS.

This paper provides a thorough research of the latest improvements in SMC for LFCP, with a concentration on MSMAIPS. With the integration of many recent highly innovative pieces of research, we aim to achieve a controller that can adapt to many PS and fix the SMC chattering problems for optimized LFC behavior.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF TWO-SOURCE, MULTI-AREA POWER SYSTEM

The examined system is a two-source, multi-area power system (TSMAPS) consisting of two generation sources in each area and a total of three areas. Figure 1 represents all the components of the TSMAPS. The subsections show the mathematical state-space expressions of all areas.

2.1. Area 1's system model

A control area within a power system often integrates both thermal (with a non-reheat turbine) and hydro generating units, each with distinct dynamic characteristics. While the thermal unit provides a simplified dynamic response, the hydropower plant offers rapid response capabilities essential for absorbing sudden load changes. Area 1's dynamic equations are derived below.

$$\Delta P_{tie,1} = \Delta P_{tie,12} - \Delta P_{tie,31} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta \dot{f}_1 = -\frac{1}{T_{P1}} \Delta f_1 + \frac{K_{P1}}{T_{P1}} \Delta P_{m1} + \frac{K_{P1}}{T_{P1}} \Delta P_{m2} - \frac{K_{P1}}{T_{P1}} \Delta P_{tie,1} - \frac{K_{P1}}{T_{P1}} \Delta P_{L1} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m1} = -\frac{1}{T_{T1}} \Delta P_{m1} + \frac{1}{T_{T1}} \Delta P_{g1} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{g1} = -\frac{1}{T_{G1}} \Delta P_{g1} - \frac{1}{T_{G1}} \Delta P_{c1} - \frac{1}{R_1 T_{G1}} \Delta f_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m2} = -\frac{2}{T_{W1}} \Delta P_{m2} + \frac{2}{T_{W1}} \Delta P_{v2} - 2 \Delta \dot{P}_{v2} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v2} = -\frac{1}{T_{H1}} \Delta P_{v2} + \frac{1}{T_{H1}} \Delta P_{g2} + \frac{T_{R1}}{T_{H1}} \Delta \dot{P}_{g2} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{g2} = -\frac{1}{T_{G2}} \Delta P_{g2} - \frac{1}{T_{G2}} \Delta P_{C1} - \frac{1}{R_2 T_{G2}} \Delta f_1 \quad (7)$$

$$A \dot{C} E_1 = \Delta P_{tie,1} + B_1 \Delta f_1 \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{tie,1} = \Delta \dot{P}_{tie,12} - \Delta \dot{P}_{tie,31} = 2\pi(T_{12} + T_{31})\Delta f_1 - 2\pi T_{12}\Delta f_2 - 2\pi T_{31}\Delta f_3 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v2} = -\frac{1}{T_{H1}} \Delta P_{v2} + \left(\frac{1}{T_{H1}} - \frac{T_{R1}}{T_{H1}T_{G2}}\right)\Delta P_{g2} - \frac{T_{R1}}{T_{H1}T_{G2}} \Delta P_{C1} - \frac{T_{R1}}{R_2 T_{H1}T_{G2}} \Delta f_1 \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m2} = -\frac{1}{T_{W1}} \Delta P_{m2} + \left(\frac{2}{T_{W1}} + \frac{2}{T_{H1}}\right)\Delta P_{v2} + \left(\frac{2T_{R1}}{T_{H1}T_{G2}} - \frac{2}{T_{H1}}\right)\Delta P_{g2} + \frac{2T_{R1}}{T_{H1}T_{G2}} \Delta P_{C1} + \frac{2T_{R1}}{R_2 T_{H1}T_{G2}} \Delta f_1 \quad (11)$$

Figure 1. State-space model of the TSMAPS power system

2.2. Area 2's system model

The reheat thermal unit is an efficient base-load generator, but its reheat stage introduces a slower, more complex dynamic response than a non-reheat turbine. Integrating this slow-responding plant with a

fast-acting hydro plant demands a sophisticated and robust LFC strategy to harmonize their contrasting dynamics. The dynamic equations are also derived below.

$$\Delta P_{tie,2} = \Delta P_{tie,23} - \Delta P_{tie,12} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m3} = -\frac{1}{T_{RH1}} \Delta P_{m3} + \frac{1}{T_{RH1}} \Delta P_{v3} + K_{R1} \Delta \dot{P}_{v3} \quad (13)$$

$$\Delta \dot{f}_2 = -\frac{1}{T_{P2}} \Delta f_2 + \frac{K_{P2}}{T_{P2}} \Delta P_{m3} + \frac{K_{P2}}{T_{P2}} \Delta P_{m4} - \frac{K_{P2}}{T_{P2}} \Delta P_{tie,2} - \frac{K_{P2}}{T_{P2}} \Delta P_{L2} \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v3} = -\frac{1}{T_{T2}} \Delta P_{v3} + \frac{1}{T_{T2}} \Delta P_{g3} \quad (15)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{g3} = -\frac{1}{T_{G3}} \Delta P_{g3} - \frac{1}{T_{G3}} \Delta P_{C2} - \frac{1}{R_3 T_{G3}} \Delta f_2 \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m4} = -\frac{2}{T_{W2}} \Delta P_{m4} + \frac{2}{T_{W2}} \Delta P_{v4} - 2 \Delta \dot{P}_{v4} \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v4} = -\frac{1}{T_{H2}} \Delta P_{v4} + \frac{1}{T_{H2}} \Delta P_{g4} + \frac{T_{R2}}{T_{H2}} \Delta \dot{P}_{g4} \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{g4} = -\frac{1}{T_{G4}} \Delta P_{g4} - \frac{1}{T_{G4}} \Delta P_{C2} - \frac{1}{R_4 T_{G4}} \Delta f_2 \quad (19)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m3} = -\frac{1}{T_{RH1}} \Delta P_{m3} + \left(\frac{1}{T_{RH1}} - \frac{K_{R1}}{T_{T2}} \right) \Delta P_{v3} + \frac{K_{R1}}{T_{T2}} \Delta P_{g3} \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v4} = -\frac{1}{T_{H2}} \Delta P_{v4} + \left(\frac{1}{T_{H2}} - \frac{T_{R2}}{T_{H2} T_{G4}} \right) \Delta P_{g4} - \frac{T_{R2}}{T_{H2} T_{G4}} \Delta P_{C2} - \frac{T_{R2}}{R_4 T_{H2} T_{G4}} \Delta f_2 \quad (21)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m4} = -\frac{2}{T_{W2}} \Delta P_{m4} + \left(\frac{2}{T_{W2}} + \frac{2}{T_{H2}} \right) \Delta P_{v4} + \frac{2 T_{R2}}{T_{H2} T_{G4}} \Delta P_{C2} + \left(\frac{2 T_{R2}}{T_{H2} T_{G4}} - \frac{2}{T_{H2}} \right) \Delta P_{g4} + \frac{2 T_{R2}}{T_{H2} T_{G4} R_4} \Delta f_2 \quad (22)$$

$$\Delta P_{tie,3} = \Delta P_{tie,31} - \Delta P_{tie,23} \quad (23)$$

2.3. Area 3's system model

The gas power plant's rapid-response capability, due to its fast-acting turbine dynamics, makes it an invaluable resource for managing sudden load fluctuation. However, this dynamic integration introduces a new layer of complexity that must be rigorously addressed to ensure controller stability. The equations of this area's dynamic are derived below.

$$\Delta \dot{f}_3 = -\frac{1}{T_{P3}} \Delta f_3 + \frac{K_{P3}}{T_{P3}} \Delta P_{m5} + \frac{K_{P3}}{T_{P3}} \Delta P_{m6} - \frac{K_{P3}}{T_{P3}} \Delta P_{tie,3} - \frac{K_{P3}}{T_{P3}} \Delta P_{L3} \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m5} = -\frac{1}{T_{RH2}} \Delta P_{m5} + \frac{1}{T_{RH2}} \Delta P_{v5} + K_{R2} \Delta \dot{P}_{v5} \quad (25)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v5} = -\frac{1}{T_{T3}} \Delta P_{v5} + \frac{1}{T_{T3}} \Delta P_{g5} \quad (26)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{g5} = -\frac{1}{T_{G5}} \Delta P_{g5} - \frac{1}{T_{G5}} \Delta P_{C3} - \frac{1}{R_5 T_{G5}} \Delta f_3 \quad (27)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m6} = -\frac{1}{T_{CD}} \Delta P_{m6} + \frac{1}{T_{CD}} \Delta P'_{v6} \quad (28)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}'_{v6} = -\frac{1}{T_F} \Delta P'_{v6} + \frac{1}{T_F} \Delta P_{v6} - \frac{T_{CR}}{T_F} \Delta \dot{P}_{v6} \quad (29)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v6} = -\frac{1}{Y_G} \Delta P_{v6} + \frac{1}{Y_G} \Delta P_{g6} + \frac{X_G}{Y_G} \Delta \dot{P}_{g6} \quad (30)$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{g6} = -\frac{c_g}{b_g} \Delta P_{g6} - \frac{1}{b_g} \Delta P_{C3} - \frac{1}{R_6 b_g} \Delta f_3 \tag{31}$$

$$AC E_3 = \Delta P_{tie,3} + B_3 \Delta f_3 \tag{32}$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{tie,3} = \Delta \dot{P}_{tie,31} - \Delta \dot{P}_{tie,23} = 2\pi(T_{31} + T_{23})\Delta f_3 - 2\pi T_{31}\Delta f_1 - 2\pi T_{23}\Delta f_2 \tag{33}$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{m5} = -\frac{1}{T_{RH2}} \Delta P_{m5} + \left(\frac{1}{T_{RH2}} - \frac{K_{R2}}{T_{T3}}\right) \Delta P_{v5} + \frac{K_{R2}}{T_{T3}} \Delta P_{g5} \tag{34}$$

$$\Delta \dot{P}_{v6} = -\frac{1}{Y_G} \Delta P_{v6} + \left(\frac{1}{Y_G} - \frac{X_G c_g}{Y_G b_g}\right) \Delta P_{g6} - \frac{X_G}{Y_G b_g} \Delta P_{C3} - \frac{X_G}{R_G Y_G b_g} \Delta f_3 \tag{35}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \dot{P}'_{v6} = & -\frac{1}{T_F} \Delta P'_{v6} + \left(\frac{1}{T_F} + \frac{T_{CR}}{T_F Y_G}\right) \Delta P_{v6} + \left(\frac{T_{CR} X_G c_g}{T_F Y_G b_g} - \frac{T_{CR}}{T_F Y_G}\right) \Delta P_{g6} + \frac{T_{CR} X_G}{T_F Y_G b_g} \Delta P_{C3} \\ & + \frac{T_{CR} X_G}{R_G T_F Y_G b_g} \frac{T_{CR} X_G}{T_F Y_G b_g} \frac{T_{CR} X_G}{T_F Y_G b_g} \frac{T_{CR} X_G}{T_F Y_G b_g} \Delta f_3 \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

3. OBSERVER DESIGN

A state observer is a control mechanism that delivers an approximation of the numerical internal states of a specific real system, TSMAPS in this scenario, by utilizing measurements taken from both the input and output of that system. First, state-space expression of the system is expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\chi}_i(t) = A_i \chi_i(t) + B_i u_i(t) + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N H_{ij} \chi_j(t) + F_i \Delta P_{Li} \\ y_i(t) = C_i \chi_i(t) \end{cases} \tag{37}$$

with, χ_I is a state vector with p state variables. Matrices A_I with dimensions of p×p. u_I is a control vector with m control variables. Matrices B_I with dimensions of p×m. χ_J is a state vector connecting to another area. Matrices H_{ij} with dimensions equal to the state variable χ_I . ΔP_{Li} is a load disturbance vector with g load disturbance variables. Matrices F_I with dimensions of p×g. y_I is an output vector with h output variables. Matrices C_I with dimensions of h×p.

Then, state-space expression of the observer is expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\hat{\chi}}_i(t) = A_i \hat{\chi}_i(t) + B_i u_i(t) + \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N H_{ij} \hat{\chi}_j(t) + L_i [y_i(t) - \hat{y}_i(t)] \\ \hat{y}_i(t) = C_i \hat{\chi}_i(t) \end{cases} \tag{38}$$

With, $\hat{\chi}_I(t)$ is the estimated state of $\chi_I(t)$. $\hat{y}_I(t)$ is the estimated state output of $y_I(t)$. L_I is the observer gain.

4. INTEGRAL SMC

Integral sliding mode control (ISMC) with a state estimator is a robust control method to enhance the stability and performance of PS. First step is to determine the integral sliding surface (ISS). The next step is the construction of an equivalent control law and a switching law. Finally, stability analysis of the control signal. The ISS with estimated state is given as:

$$\sigma_I[\hat{\chi}_i(t)] = G_i \hat{\chi}_i(t) - \int_0^t G_i (A_i - B_i K_i) \hat{\chi}_i(\tau) d\tau \tag{39}$$

With, matrices G_I is chosen accordingly to ensure that the matrix $G_I B_I$ is nonsingular or invertible. Therefore, matrix G_I can be chosen as $G_I = B_I^{-1}$

The general control signal is given (40).

$$u_i(t) = u_i^{eq}(t) + u_i^{sw}(t) \tag{40}$$

With, $u_i^{eq}(t)$ is the equivalent control equation (ECE) to ensure that the system is in the sliding surface and $u_i^{sw}(t)$ is the switching control equation that ensures the system will heads towards and remains on the sliding surface.

From (39) when $\sigma_i(t) = \dot{\sigma}_i(t) = 0$, the ECE becomes:

$$u_i^{eq}(t) = -(G_i B_i)^{-1} \left[G_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N H_{ij} \hat{\chi}_j(t) + G_i L_i [y_i(t) - \hat{y}_i(t)] + G_i B_i K_i \hat{\chi}_i(t) \right] \quad (41)$$

The switching control occurs when:

$$u_i^{sw}(t) = -\alpha_i \text{sat}[\sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)]] \quad (42)$$

α_i : positive constant ($\alpha_i > 0$). This factor helps to adjust the convergence speed of the system. The saturation condition that helps reduce chattering effect is given (43).

$$\text{sat}[\sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)]] = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } \sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)] < (-1) \\ \sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)] & \text{if } (-1) < \sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)] < 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } \sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)] > 1 \end{cases} \quad (43)$$

Substitute (43) and (44) into (42), we will have the general control signal is given below:

$$u_i(t) = -(G_i B_i)^{-1} \left[G_i \sum_{j \neq 1}^N H_{ij} \hat{\chi}_j(t) + G_i L_i [y_i(t) - \hat{y}_i(t)] + G_i B_i K_i \hat{\chi}_i(t) + \alpha_i \text{sat}(\sigma_i[\hat{\chi}_i(t)]) \right] \quad (44)$$

Using (44) we will have $\sigma_i(t)\dot{\sigma}_i(t) < 0$. This condition will ensure that the value of $\sigma_i(t)$ will decrease over time, thereby ensuring that the sliding motion will be asymptotically stable over time.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation will provide the proposed controllers' response with a comparison of other controllers such as PID and ISMC. Areas of PS model are introduced to a load disturbance of follows: $\Delta P_{L1} = 0.02$ (p.u.MW), $\Delta P_{L2} = 0.04$ (p.u.MW), $\Delta P_{L3} = 0.03$ (p.u.MW) at the time $t = 0s$. Figures 2 to 4 show the change in frequency of areas respectively to three areas. Figures 5 to 7 show the change in tie-line power of the areas.

It can be seen that the frequency deviation of the TSMAPS using the SOISMIC controller, ISMC, and the LQR method is within the allowable range and achieves optimal control efficiency. The difference mainly follows the trend: The PID controller converges to zero. The ISMC and SOISMIC give out a larger spike than PID in areas 1 and 3 (max of PID is at -0.14 Hz in area 2) in the instance load disturbance is introduced. Nevertheless, the SMC controllers oscillate less in three areas, reach the stabilized state, and stay there more stable than PID.

Figure 2. Area 1's frequency deviation using three controllers

The change in tie-line power of three areas gives out interesting features. Despite the robustness and fast reactivity of SMC, PID stabilizes and reaches stability of tie-line faster with fewer oscillations (20 s of PID compared with 40 s of SMCs). The area of highly complex plants (area 3) gives out much more vigorous stabilization of the tie-line, making SMC controllers overshoot and undershoot reaching stability.

Figure 3. Area 2's frequency deviation using three controllers

Figure 4. Area 3's frequency deviation using three controllers

Figure 5. Area 1's tie-line power deviation using three controllers

Figure 6. Area 2's tie-line power deviation using three controllers

Figure 7. Area 3's tie-line power deviation using three controllers

6. CONCLUSION

This article offers a detailed examination of SMC used for LFC in a combined multi-sources power system. Through thorough simulations and evaluations of performance, numerous important discoveries have highlighted the effectiveness of SOISMCM. Firstly, SOISMCM showed better resilience in preserving system frequency stability than traditional control approaches. Furthermore, the SOISMCM approach successfully integrated hydro and thermal power plants in a single control framework. This combination, along with the simulation shows that the suggested control approach successfully minimizes the frequency variations despite changing load conditions and disturbances, and guarantees that both kinds of power plants can effectively aid in frequency regulation, enhancing the system's overall performance. To sum up, the SOISMCM technique is shown to be a strong and dependable approach for regulating the behavior of power systems that includes hydro and thermal power plants. This study offers valuable perspectives on improving the stability and efficiency of SMC-based controllers, which will result in more robust and flexible energy management tactics in the future. Possible further work should include implementation of hardware-related SMC-based controllers so as to precisely test and verify the designed controllers.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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